

Quantum Versus Classical Entropy and Root Stochasticity

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 2, 2020

Shannon's entropy equation may be employed to calculate entropy in classical statistical mechanics with the normalized Boltzmann distribution serving as probability. In the quantum case, spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ (for a bound state) where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction is sometimes used instead, although we argue there are various other probabilities and conditional probabilities such as $P(p/x)$, $P(p/x)P(x)=P(p \text{ intersection } x)$ and $a(p1)\exp(ip1x)a(p2)\exp(ip2x)$ (i.e. addend pieces from the spatial density expression). Thus, one may ask which probability should be used? Furthermore, in classical physics, a particle is identified by p and x , leading to the idea of phase space. In this note, we argue that stochasticity is the important feature when choosing a probability to utilize in Shannon's entropy formula. We also note that although classical statistical mechanics deals with many particles and quantum mechanics with one (for a single particle bound state), one may consider a single classical particle having a momentum distribution at different x points. We attempt to compare these two cases. The classical statistical system is based on stochastic two body collisions with the effect of a nonstochastic potential added. In quantum mechanics, we argue the potential is stochastic and one need consider two momenta $p1$ and $p2$ after a stochastic hit within a δx .

Classical Statistical Mechanics with a Focus on One Particle

Classical statistical mechanics deals with numerous particles and so the concept of density is clear (i.e. the number of particles in a little volume). One may, however, focus on a single particle in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas as it moves through a region with a potential $V(x)$. Stochastic hits occur due to two body collisions and there is the usual acceleration due to $V(x)$. The probability for the particle to have a momentum p at x is

$$P(p \text{ intersection } x) = P(p)P(x) = C \exp(- (p^2/2m + V(x))/T) \quad ((1)).$$

If a single particle is at $x1$, the relative probability to be at $x2=x1+b$, where b is tiny, is:

$$P(p,x2) = P(p,x1) \exp(- (p^2/2m + V(x2))/T) / \exp(- (p^2/2m + V(x1))/T) = P(p,x1) (1 - b/T dV/dx) \quad ((2))$$

The change in average kinetic energy between $x1$ and $x2$ is:

$$KE_{ave}(x2) - KE(x1) = - KE_{ave}(x1) b/T dV/dx = .5 b \text{ Force in 1 dimension} \quad ((3))$$

KE_{ave} contains both forward and backward motion. If only forward motion is considered ((3)) becomes: $.5KE(x2) - .5KE(x1) = .25 b \text{ Force in 1 dimension}$.

Here we see a factor of .5 in a Newton like equation. The factor becomes .25 if one considers only forward motion and multiplies ((3)) by .5. It may be noted that in the classical statistical system, particles undergo stochastic two body hits in addition to the effects of $V(x)$, so there is no reason, a priori, to expect Newton's law, using only $V(x)$, to hold. (In quantum mechanics, stochastic hits arise from a potential which is $V(x)$ on average, so in that case, conservation of energy holds and one may obtain a Newton like equation by taking d/dx .)

In addition, consider only forward motion in the classical statistical case and evaluate: $KE1_{ave} + V(x)_{ave}$ and $KE2_{ave} + V(x+b)_{ave}$.

$$KE1_{ave} + V(x)_{ave} = KE1_{ave} - b/T \frac{dV}{dx} KE1_{ave} + V(x)_{ave}(1-b/T \frac{dV}{dx})$$

$$0 = -b/T \frac{dV}{dx} KE1_{ave} - V(x)_{ave}(b/T) \frac{dV}{dx} \text{ This suggests } E1=0 \text{ which it is not.}$$

A Newton's law equation may be obtained from a momentum distribution at x in quantum mechanics i.e. by taking d/dx of:

$$\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m P(p/x) + V(x) = E \text{ where } P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x).$$

Thus, there are differences between classical and quantum statistical mechanics in terms of changes of kinetic energy from one point to another, and also in the stochastic behaviour of the two schemes.

Various Probabilities in Quantum Mechanics and Stochasticity

Shannon's entropy density i.e. $\text{Sum over } i \quad -P(i)\ln(P(i))$ requires a probability. In classical statistical mechanics there is only one probability, but in quantum mechanics, it seems there may be several candidates. First of all, there are the usual $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a(p)a(p)$ (for bound states). One may, however, formulate the conditional probability $P(p/x)$ and $P(p \text{ intersection } x) = P(p/x)P(x)$ etc. This begs the question: What probability should one use? $P(p \text{ intersection } x)$ seems closest to the classical statistical mechanical situation, but we argue one should be concerned with the root stochasticity in the problem. For example, if Shannon's entropy is applied to a tossed coin, one is interested in the probability of heads or tails. This is the root stochasticity in the problem. One might argue that groupings of three tosses may also yield a probability, but this is not used as it is not a root stochasticity. In classical statistical mechanics, the stochasticity follows from two body scattering, but a momentum p_1 resulting from a hit at x_1 changes to p_2 at x_2 with $p_1^2/2m + V(x_1) = p_2^2/2m + V(x_2)$. Thus, x_1 and x_2 are linked and the probability $P(p,x)$ is required i.e. $C \exp(-(p^2/2m + V(x))/T)$. If one considers a situation with $V(x)=0$, then only $P(p)$ is needed because a particle with momentum p moves through space without being altered.

One may ask: Where is the stochasticity in a quantum bound state? In a quantum system, we argue that $V(x)$ is only an average and really corresponds to $\text{Sum over } k \quad V(k)\exp(ikx)$. Thus, there are stochastic hits in time which create a momentum distribution at x given by:

$$P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad ((4))$$

One further has: $\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} P(p/x) + V(x) = E$ ((5)) so taking d/dx yields an equation with $-dV/dx$ i.e. the average force. This equation is identical to evaluating:

$$\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} P(p/x+b) - \sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} P(p/x) \quad ((6))$$

Thus, at x , there is a relative probability $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)$ to have a momentum of p_1 , but a stochastic hit from $V(x)$ changes this probability to $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1(x+b))$ at $x+b$. One expects stochastic potential hits to occur within a region dx because otherwise the potential is not acting on the particle. This is where the stochasticity lies in quantum mechanics, we argue. Thus, a momentum p_1 changes to p_2 somewhere within dx of x . As a result, we consider a stochastic root probability of: $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ ((7)) which is consistent with integrating over dx . Integrating over dx and summing on p_1 and p_2 yields 1. One may ask why $V(x)$ does not come into the picture as it does in classical statistical mechanics. Once a stochastic hit has occurred, a particle moves freely, until the next stochastic hit occurs, so we think ((7)) is the root stochastic probability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that when using Shannon's entropy formula, one needs to choose probabilities directly related to a root stochasticity. In quantum mechanics, there are various probabilities, such as $P(x)$, $P(p)$, $P(p/x)$, $P(p/x)P(x)=P(x \text{ intersection } p)$ and $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x) a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$. We argue that momentum changes from a stochastic potential represent the root stochasticity because a momentum p_1 at x_1 changes to p_2 within dx of x_1 due to such a hit. Both p_1 and p_2 are stochastic, one at x_1 and one at x_1+b where b is tiny, so we use the product. This also yields a probability which may be integrated over dx . $P(p/x)$ only holds at a specific x . We have compared this approach with that used in classical statistical mechanics.